

COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON THE TIME-DEPENDENT INELASTIC IN-PLANE SHEAR DEFORMATION OF COMPOSITES AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

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1 Introduction

Compared to metallic materials, carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) show a much faster degradation of their mechanical properties under fire conditions. In the case of structural materials in aerospace applications it is very important to know and understand their mechanical behavior under these conditions. Since the occurring temperatures are much higher than the usual operating temperatures of CFRP these materials show complete different properties regarding their strength and stiffness and their time-dependence.

Extensive research has been done to evaluate the relationship of the mechanical properties and the surrounding temperature of fiber reinforced plastics [1-4]. Less work has been done to investigate the time-dependent deformation caused by several effects such as viscoelasticity, viscoplasticity, damage and pyrolysis at temperatures above the glass transition temperature (T_g). Most authors focused only on some of these aspects [5, 6] or did not analyze them at elevated temperatures above T_g [7]. In order to have a complete picture of all effects influencing the mechanical response of composites under thermo-mechanical loads it is important to consider the named aspects in this temperature range.

In this work the inelastic in-plane shear deformation of carbon fiber reinforced plastics is investigated during short-term creep-recovery tests under elevated temperatures and by means of microscopic crack and chemical analysis to account for the effects of damage and matrix decomposition on the time-dependent response of this material.

2 Experiments

2.1 Materials

The two materials under investigation, HEXCEL M18-1/G947 and M18-1/G939, are carbon/ epoxy prepregs used in aerospace applications. Containing the same matrix they differ in their fiber reinforcement since one has a quasi-unidirectional reinforcement with 97 % of carbon fibers in warp and 3 % glass fibers in weft direction. The other one shows a 4H-satin weave with half of the carbon fibers in weft and the other in warp direction. This permits also the analysis of the influence of the fiber reinforcement on the time-dependent behavior regarding in-plane shear.

The matrix is a combination of an epoxy and a high-temperature thermoplastic material increasing T_g and thus leading to an improved hot-wet performance.

2.2 Experimental and Analytical Devices

For performing the creep-recovery tests a state-of-the-art creep testing machine has been utilized. The special features of this device are:

- five test stations each equipped with an electro-mechanical actuator with a maximum load of 20 kN in tension and 5 kN in compression,
- a climate chamber with a possible temperature range of -50°C – 350°C and a maximum relative humidity of 95% at a maximum temperature of 90°C and
- an optical strain measurement system enabling the detection of longitudinal as well as transversal deformations of rectangular flat specimen.

Since it is also possible to perform regular quasi-static tensile tests with strain rates of up to 120 mm/min, so-called constant strain rate tests can also be performed.

In order to analyze the effect of damage the evolution of micro cracks in the resin is investigated using optical microscopes as well as a micro focus computed tomography machine where a small tensile load can be applied to the specimen after creep testing in order to re-open already developed cracks for better visibility.

The decomposition of the matrix with increasing test temperatures is studied by:

- comparing the weight of the specimen before and after the tests and
- comparing their infrared spectrum obtained with Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy showing the amount of decrease of the epoxy as well as of the thermoplastic portion.

Furthermore the orientation change of the originally $\pm 45^\circ$ oriented fibers is studied as well.

2.3 Testing and modeling

Short-term creep tests are performed with a duration of 2 hours and a recovery time of 8 hours at temperatures ranging from 100°C – 300°C . The applied tensile loads range from 10% to 50% of the ultimate quasi-static tensile strength. In order to account for the developing viscoplastic deformation cyclic loading tests with increasing load times and very long unloading intervals are done to study the enduring plastic deformation. Constant strain rate tests show at which tensile loads and strains respectively at a certain temperature viscoelastic effects occurred contributing to the inelastic mechanical response.

The creep curves are fitted using the non-linear viscoelastic materials model first developed by Lou and Schapery [8]. To account for viscoplastic deformation the model of Zapas and Crissman [9] is utilized. All necessary parameters of these two models can be determined by the tests mentioned before.

3 Results

This work shows that the inelastic time-dependent in-plane shear deformation behavior in tension at elevated temperatures up to temperatures above the glass transition temperature is influenced by manifold effects, such as viscoelasticity, viscoplasticity, micro damage and matrix decomposition. Hence in order to understand the mechanical response of fiber reinforced plastics at elevated temperatures all those aspects need to be considered.

Future research should therefore attempt to develop comprehensive test and modeling methods to minimize the effort in obtaining the necessary material data.

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